

In 1996, a second workshop was held to present test results from the latest thresher prototype and to discuss the commercial production of the thresher/cleaner. To reflect the integrated approach to product development, the name "ASI" was chosen, derived from ADRAO/SAED/ISRA, for the three agencies involved in Senegal (WARDA's French acronym is ADRAO). Then, in addition to the artisans, an agricultural machinery firm, SISMAR, was given the technical plans for the thresher/cleaner. Investing its own capital, SISMAR built a new

prototype, and assisted the WARDA/SAED/ISRA team in the tests and development of recommendations for the remaining modifications.

The ASI was officially released for commercial distribution on 5 November 1997. SISMAR has already manufactured machines for use in the Senegal River Valley and is unable to meet demand. Among the first purchasers of the ASI were two Senegalese farmers—local seed producers—who had participated in the tests and were impressed by the ASI performance rate, ease and safety of use, and quality of

output. Using the collaborative approach, this research and development effort was able to produce an adapted technology that addresses postharvest constraints with a domestically produced and easily repaired thresher/cleaner. Collaborative research by IRRI, ISRA, SAED, and WARDA was critical to ensuring a well-built, durable machine. The private sector, both artisans and the agroindustrial firm SISMAR, as well as farmers and their organizations, will determine the final diffusion of this machinery in Senegal. ■

Polyurethane rollers: a substitute for rubber rollers in rice dehuskers

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Thermoplastic polyurethane is formed by linking polyol and isocyanate. After a reaction, polyol becomes flexible and highly hydrophobic, and forms hydrolysis-stable polyurethanes. These two compounds, when mixed and undergoing reactions in different proportions and conditions, result in a polyurethane product of various hardness, tensile strength, elongation, and abrasion resistance. This polyurethane has applications in various industries such as automobiles, cold storage, footwear, etc. The major quality of polyurethane products is their abrasive resistance, which is approximately three times that of products made of rubber. In our study, polyurethane pieces were produced and tested to assess their suitability for replacing rubber rollers in rice dehuskers. The rubber rollers require frequent replacement because of the abrasive nature of the rice surface.

Polyol and isocyanate were mixed in different proportions (100:45, 100:50, 100:55, and 100:60) without any air bubbles forming in the mixture. This mix, poured in a mold for making test

Physical and mechanical properties of polyurethane specimens of various proportions of polyol and isocyanate and curing durations.

Curing duration (h)	Composition polyol:isocyanate	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Hardness (°A)	Abrasion loss (cc 40 m ⁻¹)
2.5	100:45	6.19	158.50	82	0.35
	100:50	9.17	170.70	87	0.28
	100:55	10.00	182.90	88	0.24
	100:60	9.52	161.00	86	0.36
3.0	100:45	9.42	161.00	83	0.30
	100:50	11.20	178.05	89	0.24
	100:55	16.00	197.56	90	0.18
	100:60	12.43	170.70	87	0.32
3.5	100:45	8.00	143.90	83	0.30
	100:50	9.23	153.66	88	0.20
	100:55	13.38	173.70	89	0.13
	100:60	10.22	158.50	86	0.22
Commercial rubber roller		12.59	139.00	89	0.59

pieces, was cured at 90 ± 2 °C in an oven for 2.5, 3, and 3.5 h. These pieces were tested for hardness, tensile strength, elongation, and abrasion resistance using standard procedures (see table).

The table shows that all the properties required for use in the paddy dehusker-rubber roll type increased with a curing duration of 2.5 and 3 h and proportions of 100:45, 100:50, and 100:55, and decreased with 3.5 h of curing duration and proportion of

100:60. The tensile strength, elongation, and hardness of the test pieces were on a par with those of commercially available rubber rollers. The abrasion loss was in the range of 0.13-0.36 cc 40 m⁻¹ vs 0.59 cc 40 m⁻¹ for the rubber rollers. Tensile strength, elongation, and hardness were maximum at the proportion of 100:55 cured at 3 h with 0.18 cc 40 m⁻¹ of abrasion loss. This combination was thus identified as the optimum. ■

Manuscript preparation. Arrange the note as a brief statement of research objectives, a short description of project design, and a succinct discussion of results. Relate results to the objectives. Do not include abstracts. Do not cite references or include a bibliography. Restrain acknowledgments.